

The Electronic Administrative Decision and Discretion Authority Of Public Administration

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 23 ,2025</p> <p>Accepted: June 26,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Electronic Administrative Decision, Electronic Application, Public Administration, Discretionary Authority, Constrained authority, Electronic Form, Website</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15748051</p>	<p><i>This study deals with the electronic administrative decision and discretionary authority of public administration, it is known that the developments of life obliged the public administration to use technology in its administrative transactions, so the use of technological means enables the administration to issue its administrative decisions by using electronic means, that is means the administration will complete its legal actions via the Internet Accordingly.</i></p> <p><i>The electronic administrative decision is issued by the public administration, and it is the most important privilege enjoyed by the administration of managing public facilities and achieving the public interest. This idea will be clarified by explaining the concept of the electronic administrative decision, stating the requirements for issuing it, and revealing the pillars of the electronic administrative decision, which is pillar of jurisdiction, pillar of form and procedures, pillar of reason, pillar of object and pillar of aim of the decision, by indicating the way in which these pillars are available electronically, and indicating the authorities that the public administration enjoys when issuing electronic administrative decisions represented in the discretion and the constrained authority.</i></p>

Introduction

The importance of this study appears because it deals with a new legal topic, which is the electronic administrative decision and discretionary authority of the public administration. The developments of life have obligated the administration to use the technology in its administrative transactions. New developments in the administrative life obligate us to keep pace with the process of knowledge, as the human mind results technological innovations that lead to the existence of a technological revolution, so these innovations must be used to facilitate administrative life. so, the legislator must regulate developments with administrative legal texts, especially that the rules of administrative law are flexible rules. Therefore, the use of technological means makes the administration able to issue its administrative decisions using electronic means. The idea of the electronic public administration includes the public administration carrying out its function of administrative activity electronically, whether partially or completely. The public administration will undoubtedly employ the Internet and modern means of communication with its advantages to carry out its administrative tasks.

The problem with this study appears in the urgent need to apply the electronic administrative decision to public facilities, by facilitating the introduce of electronic transactions and electronic public services, so we wonder whether the authority of the administration is discretionary or constrained in this area, and we also wonder about the availability of the necessary legislation for the issuance of the electronic administrative decision, Especially since the Jordanian state relies on electronic means in managing public utilities. Therefore, there must be legislation that legitimizes the administrative decision issued by modern technological means, especially as it does not stipulate a specific form for issuing the administrative decision.

The solution to this problem lies in answering several questions as follow:

What is the electronic administrative decision?

What are the requirements for issuing an electronic administrative decision?

What is the extent of the authority of the public administration in the electronic administrative decision?

What is the pillars formal of electronic administrative decision?

What are the substantive pillars of electronic administrative decision?

As for the objectives of the study, they are to clarify the essence of the electronic administrative decision by clarifying the definition of the electronic administrative decision, and the requirements for its issuance, as well as showing the discretionary management authority that is constrained in the formal and substantive pillars of the electronic administrative decision.

The study relied on the descriptive approach in describing the legal texts and jurisprudential opinions related to the subject of the study.

2. What is the electronic administrative decision

This topic deals with the definition of an electronic administrative decision, and shows the requirements for issuing an electronic administrative decision (electronic application), as follows:

2.1 Defining the electronic administrative decision:

The electronic administrative decision is defined as the public administration receiving the electronic request on its website and the disclosure of its binding desire to issue the decision and sign it electronically, and inform the concerned person on his e-mail, with the authority it has under the laws and regulations to create a specific legal effect that is permissible and legally possible to achieve the public interest (Al-Qubeilat, 2019). The electronic administrative decision is one of the most prominent privileges that the public administration enjoys, as it is a legal act granted to it with the aim of arranging certain legal effects, and this act is carried out by the management alone without the need for the consent of the concerned parties (Al-Sharif, 2004).

Therefore, the electronic administrative decision is a method used by the public administration as it carries out its administrative activities with the aim of achieving the public interest. Information technology has played an important role by influencing administrative regulations (organizational administrative decisions) that govern individuals with their qualities, and this type of decision requires providing information to the party that issued the decision, and this information may be transmitted in a faster, less expensive, and more accurate way, using a network. Internet. As for individual administrative decisions that govern individuals on their own; technology has also affected it through the electronic application, and through the electronic notification of the applicant using e-mail (Abdul Aziz, 2013).

There is nothing that prevents the public administration from using electronic means to practice its administrative activities, as Article (4) of the Jordanian Electronic Transactions Law No. (15) of (2015) stipulates that: "A. Any ministry, public official institution, public institution, or municipality may conduct its two transactions using Electronic means, provided that the requirements for electronic transactions contained in this law and the regulations and instructions issued pursuant to it are met.

b) Each ministry, public official institution, public institution, or municipality shall, when conducting any of its transactions by electronic means, determine the provisions and procedures related to the matters set forth below in accordance with instructions issued for this purpose:

1. Create, deposit, save or issue electronic records.
2. Using the electronic signature and any other conditions related to it.
3. The security, protection, confidentiality and integrity of electronic records and transactions.
4. The date on which its transactions were conducted by electronic means.

According to Article (5) of the same law: "A. The Ministry of Digital Economy and Entrepreneurship is considered the electronic authentication body for ministries, public official institutions, public institutions, and municipalities, and it issues electronic authentication certificates for use in any of theme's transactions.

B) The Council of Ministers, upon the recommendation of the Minister of Digital Economy and Entrepreneurship, may entrust any public official body or institution or government entity with the tasks set forth in Paragraph (a) of this Article.

2.2 Requirements for issuing an electronic administrative decision (electronic application):

The issuance of the electronic administrative decision includes submitting a request from the concerned person to the administration on its website, and this request does not require a specific formality as a rule, unless the law specifies a specific form, then here the request must fulfil the formality specified by the law, and it must include the basic data that clarify the intention concerned person. Submitting the application electronically has the advantage that it reduces the error rate in the data provided, because it is submitted through the administration's website, and electronically submitting it achieves tremendous speed, but it may lead to an accumulation of requests on the administration's website, and sometimes a malfunction on the website or difficulty communicating with it and slow it down (Abdul Rahman,2020).

It is necessary to indicate the effects of the electronic application, there is a set of effects that include both the public administration and the applicant, so the rights of the applicant are represented in the presence of the forms on the administration's website, taking into account that these forms are subject to modification, change and cancellation by the administration, as required by the interest of the work, as well as the right to print a form the application from the administration's website, also has the right to use this request as a means of proof, so that he can prove his submission of the request in accordance with the conditions and procedures set by the administration in advance and at the time specified for that.

With the administration, we remind them to obtain the application form from the department's website. And he must commit to recording correct and accurate data on the website, and reinforcing his request with

personal data, which is related to the subject of the request, and then he must send all documents to the administration, and this matter is important because the issuance of the administrative decision requires that the application be strengthened with all the documents for its issuance, and the applicant must sign his request. Electronically (Abdul Rahman, 2020).

The method of expressing the will of the single administration by electronic means is as follows:

The electronic data message that includes the content of the decision is considered a means of expressing the will of the single administration with the intention of having a specific legal effect, and it shall have the legal validity established for the official document when it is issued with a digital electronic signature approved by the issuing authority. This is when the administration prepares in advance certain electronic and programmed procedures and steps in which it expresses its will to issue an enforceable administrative decision upon its issuance, as well as arranging electronic fields by preparing a pre-prepared electronic form whose use is subject to its will to issue administrative decisions, and the electronic form includes fields divided according to pillars of the administrative decision and its validity conditions, and each field contains programmed vocabulary that must be dictated by the authority responsible for issuing the administrative decision, according to legal and technical considerations that are taken into account when making the electronic form of the administrative decision to demonstrate the legality of the decision and the conditions for its validity, and forms these carries a password for a specific decision and a code related to a field pertaining to one of the pillars of the administrative decision (Al-Baz, 2004). The competent authority to issue it must fill in the fields of the electronic decision form in accordance with the procedures and steps prepared in advance and programmed on the computer. An electronic field that includes data to be filled out by the administration, and from the legal point of view, it is assumed that this form will be used by the person legally issuing the decision, the administration is the one who creates the electronic form for the decision, and it sets the necessary conditions for its use. It follows the organized procedures when filling out the electronic form to issue the administrative decision. The complete independence of the administration using the computer leads to its accountability in cases of error, which is a result that some see as an impossibility. It is legally recognized (Al-Qaisi, 2009).

The administration - in addition to making the electronic form in advance before issuing administrative decisions - must include this form a separate field in which it includes the legal basis on which the issuance of the administrative decision in terms of its subject matter (Al-Qaisi, 2009).

3. Discretionary administration authority in the electronic administrative decision

This topic deals with the discretionary administration authority and is constrained in the formal and substantive pillars of electronic administrative decision (Al-Khalilah, 2018), as follows:

3.1. The formal pillars of the electronic administrative decision

The formal pillars of the administrative decision are determined in the two components of jurisdiction and the pillar of form and procedures.

3.1.1 The jurisdiction pillar in the electronic administrative decision: jurisdiction is defined as the legal ability to practice a specific administrative work that the legislator has made the jurisdiction of a specific authority or individual (Al-Qubeilat, 2019). and competence under electronic management is not limited to the human element, but technology and information and communication technology have a role in that. For the jurisdiction pillar be correct the following elements must be available:

a. Personal element:

The personal element is available in the electronic public administration by providing the specialist with a username and a password, so that only those who have the name, and the password can enter the electronic system, and electronic control over these decisions is for the specialists to issue them in the first place through an electronic technology that does not allow others to issue these decisions.

b. The objective element:

It is intended to define the specific field in which the public administration interferes with its administrative decisions, so each administrative body issues electronic forms that include specific items specifying the subjective jurisdiction for which a decision may be issued, so that each specific subject has a specific reference that has the authority to issue a decision, and the competent authority can objectively obtain the form according to code. The electronic form does not appear on the screen of the device for those who do not have technical authority, that is, it is not possible to access the electronic program and obtain the electronic form except by the entity that has the password, or the legal authority to fill in custom and pre-prepared fields in an electronic form related to another party that is entitled only Issuing a decision regarding issues within the scope of its competence (Al-Qaisi, 2009).

C. Regionalelement:

It is intended to define the regional scope of the decision-maker's jurisdiction, so the electronic form is linked to a specific department in a specific place, and according to a password for the competent department in the geographical area, by programming the electronic form for each department according to its geographical area of competence, and no administration has the right to go beyond the geographical range allocated to it, and

the electronic system will refuse to respond to the request of the administration violating the terms of reference, and the electronic form does not appear on the screen of the competent department in place to issue the decision (Al-Qaisi, 2009).

DThe temporal element:

The jurisdiction rules may refer to how the jurisdiction is exercised in terms of time and set restrictions in this regard that should be taken into account when the administrative body exercises its authority to issue administrative decisions, so each electronic form is linked to a specific period of time, as the form is prepared to be valid within a specific period, it may be related to the period of exercising jurisdiction or the period of validity of the decision, and work in the temporal jurisdiction field of the electronic form cannot continue if its validity period expires.

There is no doubt that electronically defining jurisdiction has great benefit in reducing cases of lack of jurisdiction defect, as well as clarity of distinction between cases of the defect of simple non-jurisdiction and the defect of serious non-jurisdiction in light of the absence of overlap in the jurisdiction between the administrative authorities, and the impossibility of breaking it in using the electronic techniques to determine this electronically, however, this requires judicial jurisprudence that keeps pace with the technical developments in issuing the administrative decision in an electronic form, so that pictures of lack of jurisdiction are read in a way that is consistent with the concept of the electronic administrative decision (Al-Qubeilat, 2019).

It can be said that in electronic administration, we can overcome all cases of lack of jurisdiction, the defect of lack of temporal jurisdiction can be overcome in a way that is fast and that it fades away through the possibility of knowing the date of the end of the temporal jurisdiction or its beginning through the Internet, and the same is the case with regard to the lack of Regional jurisdiction, which can be bypassed through the adoption of the electronic administration of administrative transparency, as well as for lack of objective jurisdiction, the speed is sufficient to solve the problems that occur without objective jurisdiction Both in the scope of centralized and decentralized administration (Abdul Rahman, 2020).

3.1.2 The form and procedures pillar of the electronic administrative decision:

The form of the electronic administrative decision is defined as the external form of the decision, and procedures are the steps that are followed to issue the decision, and it must be noted that the administration is not obligated to issue its decision in a specific form or procedure as a general rule, as its authority is discretionary in this matter, unless it is required by it from the legislator will follow a specific form or procedure, so here we can say that its authority is constrained to the formalities set by the law, and the form of the decision can be taken into account through special fields in the electronic form, so that the form appears in the form, for example, the date and number of the decision, and the reasoning of the decision, and it is necessary to distinguish between the essential formalities, and secondary formalities, so that the public administration is left free to fulfil the secondary formalities. It is worth noting that some form rules and administrative procedures necessary for issuing some decisions must be reviewed, for example:

The location of the council meeting; Where it must be held in the place designated for it, otherwise its meeting will be considered invalid, and with the application of electronic management, the employees of the General Administration will find that they need to reconsider the location of the Council meeting, as the Internet allows holding meetings remotely through video conference or through dialogue and conversation rooms and access on opinions and approvals (Al-Qubeilat, 2019).

Also, the disciplinary administrative decision; the electronic administration will require a shift in the necessity for the employee who is referred to the investigation to attend to appear before the entity in charge of the investigation, there is nothing to prevent the investigation from being conducted through the Internet or electronic writing by asking the question from the investigator and the employee's response to it through a specific computer program (Al-Khalilah, 2018).

Accordingly, the transition to electronic management requires reviewing the traditional concepts of administrative decision because the computer has become a partner for the public employee in issuing the administrative decision, and the e-government system It avoids the defect that may occur by not mentioning a substantial formality, inadvertently, or failure to fulfil guarantees for individuals through the service unit and the existence of fixed and approved forms for it. There are those who believe that the administration can take an electronic form of administrative decision through the electronic medium, and these electronic forms are electronic information, that is, information with electronic characteristics in the form of text, symbols, or pictures, computer programs or other databases, but the important thing is according to what Jurisprudence and judiciary settled on it, that the electronic form is capable of retrieval in an understandable manner, that is, it is issued in a way that is understandable to the public (Abdul Rahman, 2020).

Accordingly, we can say that as long as the administration is not obligated to follow certain formalities and procedures, and that the formalities and procedures have been divided into substantial and intrinsic formalities and procedures, so the issue in the form of the electronic administrative decision differs, because the electronic

administration has determined the forms to be filled out through the electronic medium, and this requires the necessity to follow the formalism specified in the electronic administrative decision, and this leads to considering it an essential and binding element and the duty to follow when issuing the electronic decision, and failure to take into account the formalism in issuing the electronic decision makes it defective in form and subject to cancellation by the judiciary.

3.2. The substantive pillars of the electronic administrative decision:

The objective pillars of the administrative decision are the reason, the object, and the aim.

3.2.1 The reason for the electronic administrative decision

The reason for the electronic administrative decision defined as the legal or factual situation that precedes the issuance of the decision and pushes the administration to issue it (Al-Khalilah, 2018). and for the reason for the administrative decision to be correct, it must be present until the decision is issued, and this matter can be verified by including a special field in the electronic form, for the administrative decision stating the legal or factual reason that led to the issuance of the administrative decision, as well as that the reason is legitimate; that is, the public administration must base the issuance of its administrative decisions on legitimate reasons that are consistent with the law, and that is when the legislator determines the administration certain reasons for issuing its administrative decisions, so that its authority is constrained, so an electronic form for the administrative decision can be designed so that this is linked the type of decisions, and the reasons specified for them legally, the decision source cannot issue it electronically unless the existence of the reason specified by the legislator is verified, and then the electronic program alerts that the reason indicated in the field of the reason is not consistent with the legal reasons specified for issuing this type of decision and originally stored in the software program (Al-Qubeilat, 2019).

The researcher believes that the electronic administrative decision does not have the discretionary authority of the administration in the pillar of the reason based on the legislator's identification of several reasons and leaving the management free to choose the reason, and the link is that the electronic program issues the decision based on the data entered, and if it is not compatible with the programming of the electronic mediator, the electronic decision will not be issued (Abdul Rahman, 2020).

3.2.1. pillar of object the electronic administrative decision:

The object is defined as one of the pillars of the administrative decision as the effect that directly results from the issuance of an electronic administrative decision, as it is a change that occurs in the existing image before the decision is issued, and for the decision to be valid and legitimate, the following is required in the place of the administrative decision:

- it is legally permissible; That is, the effect or the object of the decision must be in accordance with all the legal rules, otherwise this object would be unlawful, and thus lead to the nullity of the administrative decision, due to a defect in its object, called the defect of violating the law.
- it is feasible; that is, the effect of the administrative decision or its location is not practically impossible to achieve, that is, an absolute impossibility, but if the effect or location of the administrative decision is impossible; this will lead to the absence of an administrative decision, as it is impossible to achieve its effect program (Al-Qubeilat, 2019).

In the electronic public administration, pillar of object can be verified from the condition above in the electronic administrative decision by assigning a field to each of them.

There are those who believe that pillar of object in the electronic administrative decision does not raise problems, initially, because the electronic program does not issue a decision that violates the legal rules, in direct violation, or that a decision is issued that involves a mistake in interpreting the legal rule by giving it a meaning other than what the legislator intended, because the program does not have the discretionary capacity, rather, it works according to a pre-programmed system, and the disadvantage of overriding authority may occur by the employee who created the program by making him issue a decision based on incorrect data (Abdul Rahman, 2020).

The researcher believes that the object in the traditional administrative decision applies to the electronic administrative decision, but they differ in terms of authorities. The employee in the traditional administrative decision has discretion in determining the region of the decision, while in the electronic administrative decision the electronic mediator cannot exercise any discretion in choosing the object of the administrative decision, being a programmer i.e., the effect is predefined.

3.2.2. pillar of aim of the electronic administrative decision:

The purpose of the administrative decision is the goal that the administration seeks to achieve, which is the public interest, and if the administration deviates from that, its decision is flawed, with the defect of deviation in the use of authority, then the authority of the administration is constrained to achieving the public interest, so it does not have any discretion in this matter. In addition, the legislator may set special goals for the administration

to strive to achieve when issuing the administrative decision, and this pillar relates to the administration's intentions, it is difficult to access this electronically, and special fields can be designed in the electronic form for the purpose pillar that varies according to whether the decision is subject to the goal allocation rule or not, if the decision is subject to it, then the field for the purpose of issuing the decision is filled in, so that the electronic program compares it with the purpose set by the legislator, and if it deviates from it, it alerts to compare it to that, and if the administrative decision is not subject to the rule of allocating objectives ; the decision issuer must include in the purpose field detailed information related to the public interest. Verifying that the pillars of the administrative decision are electronically without interference from natural persons will reduce instances of deviation from the use of authority and protect decisions from nullity (Al-Qubeilat, 2019).

So, we can say that electronic administrative decisions are suitable for implementing the idea of electronic management, administrative decisions are classified according to the extent of the freedom of their source into decisions issued based on discretionary authority and decisions issued based on unconstrained jurisdiction. So the jurisdiction of the public administration is constrained when an administrative decision is made electronically in cases where the legislator forces the competent department to act in a certain way, and when certain pre-defined conditions are met, then the administration in this case must act positively if the pre-defined legal conditions for exercising this competence are fulfilled, then the administration is obligated Legally, by making an administrative decision, it does not have the authority of discretion in this case. The administration's behaviour is predetermined by the same legal text.

So, the constrained authority is in cases in which the management authority is represented in taking predetermined decisions, without its assessment having an influence on the content and content of those decisions, so the management does not have here to estimate the extent of intervention to issue the decision (Shatnawi, 1995).

Whereas this type of decision is issued after pre-defined conditions are met; It is possible to place these conditions within an elaborate computer program that identifies the cases to which the conditions apply, decisions are issued electronically as soon as the conditions are met, and the decision is signed electronically in the name of the competent authority to issue it and with the same program. The issuance of decisions in the case of constrained jurisdiction and an electronic signature has many advantages, such as reducing time, effort, and speed in issuing decisions because of overcoming traditional obstacles and administrative red tape and eliminating favouritism and favouritism when making decisions. Computer programs do not consider any personal consideration of the applicant, or the owner of the transaction, apart from the availability of the legal conditions in the request for the administrative decision to be issued electronically, it also reduces the burden on the administration, and leads to the limitation of cases of delegation to the discretionary areas, as the exercise of the constrained authority takes place electronically. The computer program guarantees the legitimacy of the decisions issued in all cases, the legal texts cannot be automatically overridden, so it reduces the cases of administrative objection and judicial appeal of administrative decisions due to the absence of a natural person from issuing them.

The authority of the administration is discretionary if the public administration having jurisdiction is free to assess the extent of its practice when the conditions that are legally justified are fulfilled. This type of decisions issued based on a discretionary authority must pass through the natural person who represents the public administration, to make an assessment regarding it because it is not possible. A computer program should be given discretion because appreciation is one of the requirements of management, and the will can only be achieved by a natural person.

Conclusion

1. The electronic administrative decision is defined as that the public administration receives the electronic request on its website and discloses its binding desire to issue the decision and sign it electronically, and notify the concerned person on his e-mail, with the authority it has under the laws and regulations with the intention of creating a specific legal effect that is permissible and legally possible, to achieve the public interest.
2. The issuance of the electronic administrative decision includes submitting a request from the concerned person to the administration on its website, this request does not require a specific formality as a rule unless the law specifies a specific form. The request must fulfil the formality specified by the law, and this request must include the basic data, that clarifies the intention of the concerned person. But if the person submits an electronic application and the administration issues its decision electronically; It has disclosed its binding will with the intent to have a specific legal effect.
3. The formal pillars of an administrative decision are defined in the two pillars: jurisdiction, form and procedures. jurisdiction is defined as the legal ability to carry out a specific administrative action made by the legislator under the jurisdiction of a specific authority or individual, and it has four elements: the personal, objective, regional and temporal. The form of the electronic administrative decision is defined as the external form of the decision, and the procedures are the steps that are followed to issue the decision, and

it must be noted that the administration is not obligated to issue its decision in a specific form or procedure according to the general rule, so its authority is discretionary in this matter, unless the legislator obliges it to follow a specific form or procedure, and the decision form can be taken into account through special fields in the electronic form of the administrative decision.

4. The objective pillars of the administrative decision are pillar of reason, pillar of object, and pillar of aim. The administration cannot issue decisions on its own, and for the reason for the administrative decision to be correct, it must exist until the decision is issued, and this matter can be verified through the inclusion of a field especially in the electronic form of the administrative decision, in which the legal or factual reason that led to the issuance of the administrative decision is shown. The object is defined as one of the pillars of the administrative decision as the effect that immediately and directly affects the issuance of the electronic administrative decision. as for aim pillar, special fields can be designed in the electronic form of the administrative decision for pillar of aim that varies according to whether the decision is subject to the rule of allocating objectives or not.

Recommendations

1. Simplify electronic administrative procedures.
2. Amendments all administrative legislation to keep pace with all developments.
3. The obligation to provide legal protection for those dealing with the administration. There is also a judicial control over all the administrative actions taken by the administrative body.
4. Verify the identity of the customer with the administrative authority to prevent any fraud or fraud.
5. Developing the necessary programs to eliminate electronic illiteracy.

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